

*a non-profit environmental and
climate research institute*

*Thormøhlens gate 47,
N-5006 Bergen
Norway*

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**TRAKT-2018: TRANSFERABLE KNOWLEDGE AND
TECHNOLOGIES FOR HIGH-RESOLUTION
ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND
MANAGEMENT**

INTERMEDIATE PROJECT REPORT

by

Igor Esau (ed.)

and

**Viktoria Miles, Tobias Wolf, Alexander Mahura, Riisto Makkinen, Hanna K.
Lappalainen, Natalia Gnatiuk, Alexandra Manvelova, Viktor Gorny, Pavel
Konstantinov, Mikhail Varentsov, Vladimir Masloboev**

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Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Thormøhlens gate 47

N-5006 Bergen - NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 20 58 00 Fax. +47 55 20 58 01

E-mail: admin@nersc.no Web.site: <http://www.nersc.no>

*a non-profit national environmental
and climate research institute*

REPORT

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SUMMARY The main objective of the project is to implement a novel technology for the high-resolution environmental impact assessment. Responsible and sustainable environmental management requires accurate high-resolution environmental information on the user-relevant scales. Unfortunately, such information is fragmented and inconsistent. This report describes the data sets collected to advance observation and communication technologies of open access data to support this process informing decisions on required 0.1-1 km scales.	
APPROVAL <i>Igor Esau</i>	<i>Sebastian H. Mernild, Director</i>

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Executive summary

The main objective of the TRAKT-2018 (*Transferable Knowledge and Technologies for High-Resolution Environmental Impact Assessment and Management*) project is to implement a novel technology for the high-resolution environmental impact assessment. Responsible and sustainable environmental management requires accurate high-resolution environmental information on the user-relevant scales. Unfortunately, such information is fragmented and inconsistent. Traditionally, qualitative expert judgment is used to inform the decision-making process in these circumstances. Recent advances of observation and communication technologies have opened a variety of open access data to support this process informing decisions on required 0.1-1 km scales.

The critical challenge for any high-resolution technology is to obtain coherent data sets at the spatial and time resolution matching the modeling capacity. Therefore, the second project period has been focused on collection, qualification, analysis and transfer of data in a high-latitude urbanized and industrialized area. As other small and medium cities, the case study city Apatity (North-Western Russia, Kola Peninsula) does not maintain a sufficient number of regular or citizen observations to anchor remote sensing data product assessments and modeling projections. To overcome the problem, the project partners deployed a dense meteorological network of automatic weather stations (AWS) and temperature loggers (TLs) in and around the case study city. The Urban Heat Island Arctic Research Campaign (UHIARC) network successfully provided in situ data for the chosen wintertime periods. Figure 1 shows locations of the UHIARC stations and the mean temperature over the selected period 25-29 December 2017. The remote sensing data products from different satellite platforms are less accurate and more sensitive to the total cloudiness but provide better spatial data cover as well as variety of environmental characteristics consistent of longer periods of time. In this project, we utilized MODIS (Terra/Aqua platforms), AURA, LandsAT and ASTER satellite data products. We also make use of the gridded surface type data products *ESA CCI 2015* and *GlobaLand30-2010*.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. (a) The UHIARC network of temperature sensors in Apatity. The mean temperature over 25-29 December 2017 is shown with color shading and red numbers. Courtesy: KSC. (b) The MODIS land surface temperature (LST) map for the same period generated by the ArcGIS® mapping system. Courtesy: NERSC.

Conclusions and recommendations

The project has confirmed that there is now sufficient publicly available sources of the high resolution remote sensing data to monitor the urban environment and climate in high latitude cities. Using only open source data sets, the project partners were able to demonstrate an open access ArcGIS® mapping system with geographical resolution up to the street level. The system provides surface type, land use changes, land surface temperature and biological productivity information at 0.25 – 1.0 km resolution over climatologically significant periods (since 2000). The information about upper air chemistry is provided at somewhat coarser spatial resolution but over the whole northern region. This situation will further improve when the EU COPERNICUS climate services will be fully operational.

The project demonstrated the feasibility, flexibility and usability of targeted urban meteorological observational networks. The partners have successfully deployed and maintain a low cost UHIARC network, which consists of the AWS stations and temperature loggers covering the case study area of Apatity-Kirovsk. The analysis of the UHIARC data and setup has been reported at the EGU annual meeting and submitted for peer-review and publication in *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* journal.

The project demonstrated utility of the new generation of meteorological retrospective analysis (the ERA-Interim reanalysis; open access) for statistical study of the urban anomaly regimes and assessment of potentially hazardous air quality events. These data are essential to selection of the modelling scenarios and implementation of a cost-efficient statistical – dynamical downscaling technologies.

Summarizing, we highlight that urban climate management and assessment could be run with high resolution open access data sets. The data sets are relatively easy to integrate as layers in geographical mapping and classification systems. The remote sensing data products are reliable and resolving but should be assessed through and complemented with dense urban in situ data. A variety of ready-to-use low-cost and easy-to-integrate meteorological instruments is now available to collect the required in situ data.

Recommendations from the project:

- Urban climate assessment and management can be based on the open access remote sensing data sets but require deployment of a low-cost in situ observation network for validation and calibration. The low-cost automated meteorological instruments of sufficient quality are now easily accessible.
- An urban weather station (AWS) is necessary to account for meteorological conditions in the city, urban circulations and micro-climate. Statistical correction of the data from the background station cannot account for the variable urban micro-circulations and persistent temperature and moisture differences
- Satellite data products need calibration for the specific urban conditions. Localized heat sources significantly affect details of the spatially averaged temperature fields. The high-resolution land use – land cover data sets are still insufficiently accurate and detailed. They need to be improved in the urbanized areas. Such work is ongoing in WUDAPT collaboration www.wudapt.org
- Air quality significantly varies and is sensitive to the turbulent mixing and stability of the lowest atmospheric layers. Persistent anti-cyclonic conditions trap the urban atmosphere, which would result in air quality hazards. Unfortunately, there is still no low-cost instruments and high-resolution data products to monitor the air quality in urban environment. A popular AirQualityEgg® instrument has not passed the test at NERSC.

Geographical description of the project case study area

The project case study is centered on the Apatity-Kirovsk region (Murmansk Oblast) of Russia (Figure 2). Both Apatity and Kirovsk are located in the center of the Kola Peninsula. The city of Apatity lies between lake Imandra, the largest lake in the Murmansk region, and the Khibiny mountains, with the highest peak Yudychvumchorr, 1200 meters above the sea level.

Figure 2. Landsat image of Apatity-Kirovsk study area. Stars shows location of the Automatic Weather Stations (AWS).

Apatity is the second largest city in the Murmansk region, with population of 55,713 inhabitants. Founded in 1966, the city was named after one of its most abundant natural resources, apatite, the raw mineral used in the production of phosphorous mineral fertilizers. Only 16 kilometers separate the city of Apatity from the neighboring city of Kirovsk. Kirovsk is the highest elevated mountain city on the Kola peninsula. The city was founded in 1929. Today the population of Kirovsk is approximately 28.600 people. The principal branch of the economy is mining, centered on the towns of Kirovsk and Apatity in the Khibiny Mountains. Kirovsk - open pit apatite mine, apatite processing; Apatity - coal-fired power station, nepheline waste, apatite processing

The area is located within two vegetation zones – tundra and taiga. The vertical zonation is characterized by a shift from forest-tundra low in the terrain to tundra vegetation at higher altitudes. The Khibiny Mountains are covered mostly by trees, dwarf shrubs, lichen-shrub, and lichen dominated tundra formations. The non-mountain part of the area is swampy forest, or taiga, with birch, spruce, and pine. Sphagnum bogs are widespread everywhere. Soils are thin and very poorly developed. The winter climate is extremely severe, and summers are short and cool.

Meteorological high-resolution observations in Apatity

The Urban Heat Island Arctic Research Campaign (UHIARC)

The UHIARC meteorological high-resolution observational network has been deployed in Apatity in winter 2017-2018. The microclimatological group (KSC) has successfully obtained data from the winter-spring measuring campaign in the case study city. Locations of the deployed temperature sensors (*iButton* temperature loggers, TLs) are shown in Figure 3. These TLs are popular for the spatially resolved urban climate studies, but they require careful radiation shielding. More comprehensive observations were obtained with a few automatic weather stations (AWS) *Davis Vantage Pro2* (Figure 2). Accuracy of the meteorological stations is of 0.5K. One AWS was deployed on the coast of the lake Imandra. It was collocated with the WMO R1 station (the WMO station index is 22213). *iButton* TLs have reported accuracy 0.5 K, but they require careful radiation shielding. However, the direct solar radiation is not a problem for our study since the sun was mostly under the horizon during the winter months.

Figure 3. Locations of the UHIARC temperature sensors in Apatity during winter 2017-2018. Courtesy: KSC.

During this period, *iButton* TLs were deployed at a height of 2m above the ground in the city area. Each sensor was insulated with a rubber membrane and attached by a metal wire to extended tree branches to avoid possible radiative distortion of the temperature readings. In order to avoid possible effects of solar heating on loggers during the short periods of the sunlight, the *iButton* readings were processed to remove times when the solar elevation was more than 2° , which covers about 5% of the selected period. They were distributed around different building types: in the campus – low widely spaced buildings in the natural landscape; in the central district – middle-height administrative buildings at Lenin Square and tall buildings surrounded by paved surfaces at Geologists Square; in the city’s southern part – low industrial buildings and urbanized landscapes (railway station etc.); and in the industrial zones – widely spaced low and tall structures. All sensors were set up to read the temperature at 1 hour intervals. During the short-period campaigns each AWS was co-located with an *iButton* sensor to control data quality. Intercomparison of these two types of observations confirmed that the temperature records were unbiased and maintained their respective accuracy margins.

Figure 4. Thermal loggers used for temperature profile: (a) iButton temperature loggers; and (b) an example of iButton installation at a tree branch. Photo credits: Mikhail Varentsov (b), Pavel Konstantinov (c)

Figure 5. Variations of air temperature at urban AWS site (red line) and at the WMO station (black line). Orange shading indicates the temperature difference ΔT between urban AWS site and WMO station. Blue rectangles indicate the cases with intensive urban heat island and stable stratification selected for analysis within the framework of TRACT-2018 project.

During the winter season, according to the data of automatic meteorological stations of the UHIARC network, we marked 6 episodes with high intensity of Urban Heat Island (UHI) - (Figure 5)

The obtained temperature distribution in the Apatity-Kirovsk area for the selected extreme cases (Figure 5) are shown in Figure 6. The urban heat island is clearly distinguished within the built-up area (see Table 1). The suburban areas, even differing in absolute height, are noticeably colder. This is especially evident in the eastern part of the profile, which is hypsometrically located above the rest of the other measured area. More accurate synoptic and statistical analysis of temperature differences in Apatity region will be provided during Stage #3 of the project in connection with the urban modeling scenarios.

Table 1. Urban heat island intensity in Apatity during winter campaign (based on profile measurements data).

	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7
UHI intensity, [K]	7.9	6.5	6.9	7.5	12.0

(Case 3)

(Case 4)

(Case 5)

(Case 6)

(Case 7)

Figure 6. Spatial distribution of the mean air temperature averaged over the selected cases (3 through 7) obtained from the UHIARC observations. Courtesy: KSC.

Accuracy of the satellite remote sensing data products with respect to the UHIARC data

The hyperspectral MODIS system (see the next section) performs a survey in 36 channels in the visible, near, mid, and thermal IR spectra. The LST data product uses the data of channels 31 and 32 (10.78–11.28 μm and 11.77–12.27 μm , respectively), in which the intensity of the Earth's surface thermal emission is recorded and which cover the range corresponding to the maximum intrinsic emission of the Earth (10–12 μm). The spatial resolution of images received in these channels is about 1000 m.

We recognize that the magnitude and spatio-temporal dynamics of the UHI is sensitive to the dataset used in the analysis. The meteorological observations of the surface air temperature as provided by the AWSs and iButton loggers do not necessarily refer to the same physical UHI phenomenon as the land surface temperature (LST) anomalies derived from satellite remote sensing. Therefore, we compared in-situ air temperature and MODIS LST (separately for the TERRA and AQUA platforms) for the winter of 2015/16. Figure 7 shows the rather good agreement between the LST from remote sensing and the in situ temperature observations at the R1 site. The R1 station is located on a homogenous landscape near the Imandra Lake, which is frozen in wintertime. There are somewhat weaker relationships between the LST and in-situ measurements for the temperature differences between urban and rural sites (U1 and R1) and between two different rural sites at different elevations (R4 and R1), with the determination coefficients in the range $R^2 = 0.33\text{--}0.46$ (TERRA platform) and $0.47\text{--}0.64$ (AQUA platform). Nevertheless, the data confirms that a linear approximation is satisfactory and the temperature dependences are monotonic. So, a warmer urban temperature in the in-situ data necessarily corresponds to a positive temperature anomaly in the satellite LST data.

Figure 7. The relationships between the MODIS TERRA and AQUA LST (T_{MODIS}) and the in-situ surface air temperature observations (T_{obs}) during the winter of 2015-2016 for (a) data corresponding to the R1 site; (b) data corresponding to $\Delta T_{\text{R4-R1}}$; and (c) data corresponding to the UHI intensity, $\Delta T_{\text{R1}}^{\text{U1}}$.

Satellite data analysis

List of the produced data sets

Folders and content of the file **Trakt GIS.zip**

2015-2016 -Average datasets for the selected dates.
2017 average -Average datasets for the selected dates
2017 selected – single image data for the selected dates
Ancillary data-shape data
Average data- 2000-2017 mean LST data
DEM- Aster GDEM data
LandCover-LC Geotiff and shape files
NDVI-NDVI 18-year average data
Raw data- original non-processed data
DataAnalysis- results of data analysis

Description of the remote sensing data products

We use several different MODIS products: MODIS Terra (MOD11A2) and Aqua (MYD11A2) 8 days average LST product from 2000-2017; MODIS Terra (MOD11A1) and Aqua (MYD11A1) daily product for 2013-2017 for the selected dates and MODIS NDVI product (MOD13Q1) for 2000-2017 (Table 2).

Deployed on polar-orbiting satellite platforms, Terra observes a given area twice per day and Aqua also observes the same area twice per day. For Terra-MODIS, the satellite overpass times are approximately 10:30am and 22:30pm local time and for Aqua-Modis is 13:30pm and 1:30 am. Therefore, for a specific area, four observations are available daily under clear-sky conditions. With such a dataset, the diurnal, seasonal and interannual variations of surface UHI are examined in the study.

The MODIS LST were acquired from the MODIS LST/Emissivity Daily L3 Global 1 km V005 and 006 product. Data was obtained from both the Terra (MOD11A1&A2) and Aqua (MYD11A1&A2) satellites and downloaded from <http://reverb.echo.nasa.gov/>. MOD(MYD)11A2 is an 8-day LST product of averaging from 2 to 8 days of the clear-sky MOD(MYD)11A1 daily product of Terra and Aqua-MODIS and it has 12 Science Data Set (SDS) layers. The MODIS LSTs are derived from measurements in the thermal infrared channels 31 (10.78 to 11.28 μ m) and 32 (11.77 to 12.27 μ m) using the day–night split-window algorithm.

LST composites were downloaded from <http://reverb.echo.nasa.gov/>. The downloaded data were in HDF-EOS format and in the sinusoidal projection system. The data were re-projected from the sinusoidal projection to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) zone 37°N projection system with the WGS84 datum, reformatted from HDF-EOS to GeoTIFF format and converted from °K to °C as $DN * 0.02 - 273.15$. According to the product quality control (QC) flag, the data we used had an average LST error of >2 °C. The analysis was carried out for winter (DJF) and summer (JJA) seasons. We processed day and night LST data.

MODIS LST products for selected dates

MODIS Terra (MOD11A1) and Aqua (MYD11A1) daily product from 2013 to 2017 was downloaded for the selected dates corresponding to the dates of field companies (Table 2 and Table 3). MODIS TERRA-MOD11A1 Day (crossing time 11:30) and Night (23:30) and MODIS Aqua-MYD11A1 Day (14:30). We use the new MODIS Land Surface Temperature (LST) collection 6, which provides numerous improvements compared to collection 5. However, being remotely sensed data in the thermal range, LST shows gaps in cloud-covered areas. Therefore, we have missing data for a certain part of the area for a certain date. For example, we have missing data from MODIS TERRA for 29.12.2017 (Table 4).

To reduce the data gaps and provide higher quality data for the modelling we average the data. We use temporal averaging rather than spatial. Because of a high LST contrast between different land cover types the spatial averaging can give confusion between different land cover type and give a wrong value. We

produce: average day (MODday, MYDday), average night (MODnight, MYDnight) and average day and night (MODdaynight, MYDdaynight); average MOD and MYD, day, night and daily mean.

MODIS NDVI

MODIS data were acquired for the period 2000–2017. We used the MODIS NDVI product (MOD13Q1, 250 m spatial resolution, 16-day composites produced every 16 days). NDVI data were quality-filtered by the MODIS reliability data, excluding snow- and cloud covered pixels. A 0.3-1 NDVI threshold is used to exclude water, bare soil and other non-vegetated pixel from the analysis. Growing season (JJA) maximum NDVI (NDVI_{max}) maps were compiled by selecting the maximum NDVI from each 16-day composites for each pixel. Max NDVI characterizes the maximum development of vegetation during the growing period and reduces the errors in beginning of phenological phases between different vegetation zones (Miles and Esau, 2016). The data gaps in the raster mosaic pixels were then filled with information using the nearest neighbor statistical interpolation from the surrounding pixels with data. The percentage of excluded pixels is variable. Images with a higher percentage of excluded pixels were eliminated from the analysis, usually one or two images per summer. Figure 9 shows the 16-year average NDVI values.

Statistical methods were applied to the time series of NDVI_{max} and derived parameters, to provide metrics and to identify and test for changes. Time series characteristics of interest are mean, variability and trend. Temporal linear trends in yearly summer NDVI_{max} over the study area for the period 2000–2017 were estimated using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression for each pixel stack, with year as the independent variable and NDVI as the response variable.

Land Cover data

Global land cover type data with 30 m resolution *GlobaLand30-2010*

We used *GlobaLand30-2010*, product of global land cover at 30-meter spatial resolution. The classification images used for the data generation of *GlobaLand30-2010* are mainly 30 m multispectral images, including Landsat TM and ETM+ multispectral images and images from Chinese Environmental Disaster Alleviation Satellite (HJ-1) <http://www.globallandcover.com/GLC30Download/index.aspx>. The Data consists of 10 Land Cover (LC) types: cultivated land, forest, grassland, shrubland, wetland, water bodies, tundra, artificial surface, bare land and permanent snow and ice. LC classes for the Apatity-Kirovsk area are in Table 4 and Figure 10. Using ArcGIS conversion tool, the *GlobaLand30-2010* was converted in to polygons as in Figure 11 (Data in WGS 84, UTM 37N; Resolution: 30 x30 m; Filename: ApatityKirovskLC30).

European Space Agency Climate Change Initiative land cover data *ESA-CCI-LC*

European Space Agency (ESA) *Climate Change Initiative (CCI) LC data* (<http://maps.elie.ucl.ac.be/CCI/viewer/download.php>) is also used in this study. The CCI 300 m data are annual global LC time series from 1992 to 2015. This unique dataset was produced by the reprocessing and interpretation of five different satellite missions. For the study area class typology see Table 5 and Figure 12 (Data in WGS 84, UTM 37N; Resolution: 250x250 m; Filename: ApatityKirovskLCcci).

Figure 8. Different components of the land surface temperature (LST) from MODIS averaged over the period 25-29.12.2017. Courtesy: NERSC.

Figure 9. The annual maximum MODIS NDVI averaged over 2000-2017 (18 years). Courtesy: NERSC.

Figure 10. The GlobaLand30-2010 land cover classes for the Apatity-Kirovsk study area. Class code reference is taken from Table 4.

Figure 11. GlobaLand30-2010 Land cover classes polygon

Figure 12. The ESA-CCI-2015 Land cover classes for the Apatity-Kirovsk study area. Class code reference is taken from Table 5.

Figure 13. The ESA-CCI-2015 Land cover classes polygons.

Digital elevation data.

We use the ASTER Global Digital Elevation Model (ASTER GDEM) (Figure 14). ASTER GDEM is an easy-to-use, highly accurate DEM covering all the land on earth. The ASTER GDEM V2 maintains the GeoTIFF format and the same gridding and tile structure as V1, with 30-meter postings and 1 x 1-degree tiles. ArcGIS ArcScene was used to overlay LST data over DEM (Figure 37).

Figure 14. The ASTER Digital Elevation Map for the Apatity-Kirovsk area.

Figure 15. Summer (left) and winter (right) LST overlay over DEM.

Figure 16. The NDVI overlay over DEM

Figure 17. Data overlay over DEM: a) Landsat image; b) NDVI; c) summer LST; d) winter LST.

Ancillary data

Ancillary data from sources other than remote sensing were used to assist in analysis and classification or to populate metadata. Here we used Open Street Map data to extract city shape and building location and its density.

Urban climate anomalies: Methodology

For both cities, we computed the annual mean LST per pixel by aggregating the available 8 days mean composite separately for winter and summer. The daytime and night-time UHIs were calculated separately. Both the seasonal and annual average daytime and night-time values were computed. The mean values were calculated based on the 16-year time series. As a result, we produced annual and temporally averaged summer and winter LST maps. Using ArcGIS conversion tool, the LC data was converted into polygons. The mean LST was calculated for each LC type. To explore the relation of urban temperature to the surrounding temperature using ArcGIS analysis tools, we developed a 10 km buffer from the city edge for both cities. We define the Surface UHI Intensity (UHII) as the difference of maximum urban and mean rural LST. Maximum urban area was identified as a maximum pixel value for all urban pixels in each 10 km buffer and then mean LST was calculated for all non-urban pixels.

To identify the spatial-temporal variation of temperature in the buffer in relation to urban temperature, we calculate the UHII on a per pixel basis by subtracting each pixel value from the U_{max} pixel.

$$UHII_p = LST_{Umax} - LST_{pi...n}$$

Eq. 1

To explore the effects of different LC on UHI we used CCI LC data. Types of LC (see Figure X) and LC type area size (as a percent of total) are shown in Table 5 and 6. We explore the LST seasonal and temporal variability for each LC class in a 10 km buffer from the city edge (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Representation of the 10 km buffer from the respective city edges.

The association between urban area and surround LST was established through the UHII which compares the maximum temperature of urban surfaces to that of surfaces comprising of different land cover types:

$$UHII_{LC} = LST_{Umax} - LST_{LC}$$

Eq. 2

where LST_{Umax} is the maximum surface temperature of a MODIS pixel defined as urban and LST_{LC} is the mean temperature of an alternative land cover type. The urban pixels with maximum LST was compared to the average temperature of certain land cover class of the area separately for winter and summer and for the winter/summer day and night.

(a)

(b)

Figure 19. The mean LST (MODIS) for the winter (a) and summer (b) seasons over 2000-2017 (18 years).

Figure 20. Land Cover Classes LST variability at different altitude

Figure 21. Diurnal and seasonal LST variability

Remote-sensing data analysis for air quality quantification

SO₂ content in the lower atmosphere was determined using remote-sensing data products from the AURA satellite platform. The period of analysis 2005 – 2017.

Number of OMSO ₂ e AURA digital scenes:	635
Number of Landsat-8 digital scenes:	9
Number of Sentinel-2 digital scenes:	4
Number of ASTER digital scenes:	3

All scenes were transformed to UTM projection, zone No. 36; no radiometric correction was applied for visible and nearest-infrared channels, because the data have been already calibrated.

The land surface temperature (LST) were calculated using the channels 10 and 11 of Landsat 8 with emissivity of snow cover of 0.99.

The thermodynamic LST was retrieved from the ASTER (Terra satellite) data using the model of the winter subarctic atmosphere in MODTRAN.

The geographical maps of the SO₂ content (the mean and the standard deviation) in the lower atmosphere was obtained.

Figure 22. Spatial variability of UHI.

Содержание SO2 в приземном слое атмосферы

Figure 23. The map of SO2 contents in the lower atmosphere (Dobson's units), averaged for the period of 2005-2017 years (Summer time) (according 635 digital scenes of OMSO2e AURA satellite)

Characteristics of the OMSO2e AURA product

Instrument OMI (Ozone Monitoring Instrument) onboard of the AURA satellite. Resolution: daily 0.25 x 0.25 degree per pixel, global. SO2 content is measured in the lower atmosphere, units Dobson Units [DU]. Figure 24 shows the data.

Obtained: 885 digital scenes over the summer 2005 – 2017 (**Satellite_SO2.csv**). Each year, the earliest scene is the end of May, the latest – in September.

Satellite Data for Verification of Air Pollution Modelling Results

See special report in the PDF file.

Figure 24. The OMSO2e AURA product, available data over Kola Peninsula.

Tables

Table 2. The MODIS data availability

Date	MODIS product	Data	Product type	Resolution (m)
24.11-26.02.2000-2016 (DJF)	MOD11A2 Day	8 days average	LST	1000
	MOD11A2 Night	8 days average	LST	1000
	MYD11A2 Day	8 days average	LST	1000
	MYD11A2 Night	8 days average	LST	1000
04.30.-09.29.2000-2016 (MJJAS)	MOD11A2 Day	8 days average	LST	1000
	MOD11A2 Night	8 days average	LST	1000
	MYD11A2 Day	8 days average	LST	1000
	MYD11A2 Night	8 days average	LST	1000
	MOD13Q1	16 days average	NDVI	250
DJF 2013-2014	MOD11A1 Day	Selected dates	LST	1000
	MOD11A1 Night	Selected dates	LST	1000
	MYD11A2 Day	Selected dates	LST	1000
	MYD11A2 Night	Selected dates	LST	1000
DJF 2015-2017	MOD11A1 Day	Selected dates	LST	1000
	MOD11A1 Night	Selected dates	LST	1000
	MYD11A1 Day	Selected dates	LST	1000
	MYD11A1 Night	Selected dates	LST	1000

Table 3. MODIS data availability for selected dates.

Date	MOD11A1 Day			MOD11A1 Night		
	City	Botanical garden	Tik-Guba	City	Botanical garden	Tik-Guba
11.12.15	x	x			x	
13.12.15	x	x	x			
14.12.15	x					
15.12.15	x	x	x	x	x	x
16.12.15	x	x	x	x	x	x
23.12.15	x	x	x	x	x	x
28.12.15	x	x		x	x	x
29.12.15	x	x	x	x	x	x
10.1.16	x	x	x	x	x	x
11.1.16	x	x	x	x	x	x
12.1.16	x	x	x	x	x	x
13.1.16		x				
19.1.16	x	x	x	x	x	x
20.1.16	x	x		x	x	x
21.1.16	x	x		x	x	x
22.1.16	x	x	x		x	x
23.1.16	x	x	x		x	x
28.1.16	x	x	x	x	x	x
29.1.16	x	x	x	x	x	x
1.3.16	x	x	x			
10.3.16				x	x	x
11.3.16	x	x	x	x	x	x
23.3.16	x	x	x	x	x	x
	MYD11A1 Day			MYD11A1 Night		
25.12.2017		x	x			
26.12.2017	x	x	x	x	x	x
27.12.2017	x	x	x	x	x	x
28.12.2017	x	x	x			
29.12.2017	x	x	x	x	x	x
	MOD11A1 Day			MOD11A1 Night		
25.12.2017	x	x		x	x	x
26.12.2017	x	x		x	x	x
27.12.2017	x	x		x	x	x
28.12.2017	x	x	x	x	x	x
29.12.2017						

Table 4. The GlobalLand30-2010 class typology.

Code	Type	Content
10	Cultivated Lands	Cultivated used for agriculture, horticulture and gardens, land including paddy fields, irrigated and dry farmland, vegetation and fruit gardens. etc.
20	Forest	Lands covered with trees. with vegetation cover over 30%, including deciduous and coniferous forests, and sparse woodland with cover 10 - 30%, etc.
30	Grassland	Lands covered by natural grass with cover over 10%, etc.
40	Shrubland	Lands covered with shrubs with cover over 30%, including deciduous and evergreen shrubs, and desert steppe with cover over 10%. etc.
50	Wetland	Lands covered with wetland plants and water bodies, including inland marsh, lake marsh, river floodplain wetland, forest/shrub wetland, peat bogs, mangrove and salt marsh. etc.
60	Water bodies	Water bodies in the land area, including river. lake, reservoir, fish pond, etc.
70	Tundra	Lands covered by lichen, moss, hardy perennial herb and shrubs in the polar regions, including shrub tundra, herbaceous tundra, wet tundra and barren tundra, etc.
80	Artificial Surfaces	Lands modified by human activities, including all kinds of habitation, industrial and mining area, transportation facilities, and interior urban green zones and water bodies, etc.
90	Bareland	Lands with vegetation cover lower than 10%, including desert, sandy fields, Gobi, bare rocks, saline and alkaline lands, etc.
100	Permanent snow and ice	Lands covered by permanent snow, glacier and icecap

Table 5. The ESA-CCI-LC class typology.

Code	Typology
0	No data
10	Cropland, rainfed
11	Herbaceous cover
12	Tree or shrub cover
20	Cropland irrigated or post-flooding
30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)
40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)
50	Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
60	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
61	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)
62	Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)
70	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
71	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)
72	Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen, open (15-40%)
80	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
81	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)
82	Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)
90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needleleaved)
100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)
110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)
120	Shrubland
121	Shrubland evergreen
122	Shrubland deciduous
130	Grassland
140	Lichens and mosses
150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)
151	Sparse tree (<15%)
152	Sparse shrub (<15%)
153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)
160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brakish water
170	Tree cover, flooded, saline water
180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brakish water
190	Urban areas
200	Bare areas
201	Consolidated bare areas
202	Unconsolidated bare areas
210	Water bodies

Table 6. MODIS LST for selected dates (2015-2016)

Date	MOD11A1 Day LST ° C			MOD11A1 Night LST ° C		
	City	Botanical garden	Tik-Guba	City	Botanical garden	Tik-Guba
11.12.15	-18.84	-21.02			-14.72	
13.12.15	-16.22	-18.64	-17.82			
14.12.15	-17.66					
15.12.15	-13.28	-14.26	-13.98	-17.72	-19.88	-18.06
16.12.15	-17.2	-18.36	-18.62	-13.94	-14.16	-15.48
23.12.15	-13.98	-18.04	-19.86	-20.14	-21.86	-20.5
28.12.15	-23.02	-22.52		-25.72	-27.06	-24.94
29.12.15	-19.04	-21.94	-22.08	-19.38	-21.44	-22.42
10.1.16	-25	-22.62	-25.14	-28	-26.88	-30.92
11.1.16	-30.34	-33.2	-35.78	-30.26	-33.92	-34.08
12.1.16	-36.04	-35.86	-37.12	-33.06	-34.48	-36.6
13.1.16		-27.42				
19.1.16	-25.68	-28.86	-28.62	-30.16	-31.28	-33.46
20.1.16	-32.38	-33.24		-35	-35.12	-35.6
21.1.16	-32.06	-33.02		-32.42	-32.5	-35.64
22.1.16	-19.12	-20.9	-21.06		-17.54	-19.5
23.1.16	-28.04	-28.08	-29.24		-22.68	-27.9
28.1.16	-12.58	-12.34	-16	-17.68	-20.6	-20.68
29.1.16	-14.14	-13.96	-13.68	-19.52	-18.62	-22.96
1.3.16	-15.92	-16.02	-19.86			
10.3.16				-9.04	-10.16	-12.72
11.3.16	-7.56	-11.52	-11.64	-14.82	-14.14	-17.84
23.3.16	-10.62	-10.78	-12.34	-20.1	-18.04	-20.7

Table 7. MODIS LST for selected dates (2016-2017)

Date	MYD11A1 Day LST ° C			MYD11A1 Night LST ° C		
	City	Botanical garden	Tik-Guba	City	Botanical garden	Tik-Guba
25.12.2017		-28.62	-30.56			
26.12.2017	-27.42	-30.2	-31.22	-26	-29.22	-29.22
27.12.2017	-25.14	-25.6	-26.96	-23.14	-29.88	-29.88
28.12.2017	-18.9	-18.14				
29.12.2017	-13.66	-14.7	-14.5	-23.34	-25.76	-24.14
	MOD11A1 Day LST ° C			MOD11A1 Night LST ° C		
25.12.2017	-26.08	-28.46		-25.66	-30.04	-31.38
26.12.2017	-27.16	-29		-22.08	-20.98	-23.14
27.12.2017	-21.52	-24.06	-27.48	-23.36	-22.04	-27.8
28.12.2017	-16.94	-273.3		-23.82	-26.46	-27.66
29.12.2017						

Table 8. Areas of different land cover (LC) classes and NDVI values for Apatity

Code	LC type	Area (% from total)	NDVI
11	Herbaceous cover	1.47 %	0.85
40	Mosaic natural vegetation/cropland	1.84 %	0.81
60	Tree cover, deciduous	1.10 %	0.86
70	Tree cover, needleleaved	35.66 %	0.81
90	Tree cover, mixed	5.88 %	0.86
100	Mosaic tree and shrub	9.56 %	0.81
110	Mosaic herbaceous/tree and shrub	1.10 %	0.71
120	Shrubland	2.94 %	0.71
122	Shrubland deciduous	1.84 %	0.75
150	Spare vegetation	11.40 %	0.56
180	Shrub and herbaceous flooded	4.78 %	0.79
190	Urban areas	8.46 %	0.69
200	Bare areas	2.57 %	0.36
210	Water bodies	11.40 %	0.55

Table 9. The mean LST for different land cover (LC) classes

Code	Mean LST					
	S	SD	SN	W	WD	WN
11	9.26	13.63	4.93	-17.56	-17.12	-18.00
40	9.35	13.49	5.28	-17.10	-16.74	-17.46
60	9.26	13.23	5.38	-16.32	-16.03	-16.61
70	9.02	12.74	5.39	-16.95	-16.49	-17.41
90	8.90	12.65	5.24	-16.66	-16.28	-17.03
100	9.27	13.49	5.14	-16.61	-16.28	-16.95
110	8.24	13.25	3.38	-14.75	-14.55	-14.95
120	8.81	14.03	3.74	-14.56	-14.51	-14.60
122	8.95	13.89	4.17	-15.11	-14.96	-15.26
150	8.31	13.34	3.43	-15.19	-15.01	-15.36
180	8.95	13.33	4.68	-16.48	-16.09	-16.87
190	11.60	16.54	6.71	-15.43	-15.06	-15.76
200	6.73	10.67	2.94	-15.29	-15.06	-15.53
210	8.88	10.49	7.36	-15.65	-15.13	-16.17

 Table 10. The urban heat island intensity (UHII) between T_{Umax} and T_{LC}

Code	UHII					
	S	SD	SN	W	WD	WN
11	2.34	2.91	1.77	2.12	2.06	2.23
40	2.25	3.05	1.43	1.66	1.68	1.69
60	2.34	3.31	1.33	0.89	0.97	0.85
70	2.58	3.80	1.32	1.52	1.43	1.65
90	2.70	3.89	1.46	1.22	1.22	1.27
100	2.34	3.05	1.57	1.18	1.22	1.19
110	3.36	3.29	3.32	-0.69	-0.51	-0.82
120	2.79	2.51	2.97	-0.88	-0.55	-1.16
122	2.65	2.65	2.54	-0.32	-0.09	-0.51
150	3.29	3.20	3.28	-0.25	-0.05	-0.40
180	2.65	3.21	2.03	1.05	1.03	1.11
200	4.87	5.87	3.77	-0.14	0.00	-0.24
210	2.72	6.05	-0.65	0.22	0.07	0.41

ANNEX. Complementary and extending materials

Preparation of modeling conditions and scenarios

See the following special reports in the separate PDF files

Historical data analysis for the for Apatity-Kirovsk region in Russia

SMEAR – Station for Measuring Ecosystem-Atmosphere Relations

Multi-Scales and Multi-Processes Modelling at INAR

Seamless Integrated Meteorology-Chemistry-Aerosols Enviro-HIRLAM Modelling

Process-Based Modelling for the Meteorology-Chemistry-Aerosol System

Preparation and setup of PALM LES model

The PALM LES model needs as input surface and boundary conditions, including geostrophic wind and temperature profiles. For the surface topography the best available dataset is the Arctic DEM (<https://www.pgc.umn.edu/data/arcticdem/>) that is available at a 5 m horizontal resolution. This data will serve as the basis for the PALM LES simulations. The Arctic DEM has however large data gaps in the area around Apatity. These will be substituted with conveniently available lower resolution topographic data. For this we are currently testing the Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010) with a 7.5 arcseconds horizontal resolution. The relevant tiles for both datasets are downloaded and we are working on the merger of both.

For the surface temperature heat fluxes or temperatures (PALM can calculate surface heat fluxes within each run when the surface temperature is known) two different approaches will be tested: Satellite information of surface temperatures provided by NERSC and surface heat flux data from COSMO provided by the Russian partners (Kola Science Center). Boundary conditions for a chosen time interval during the case study, including initial profiles will be provided from the COSMO runs by the Russian partners (Kola Science Center).

The necessary computer resources for the planned simulations are available via NOTUR project NN9528K, where 930 000 processor hours are available for the period 2018.1 (1 April 2018 - 31 September 2018). We assume to use less than 200 000 processor hours for the TRAKT2018 case study.

Dissemination and outreach

See the following special reports in the separate PDF files

PEEX – Pan-Eurasian EXperiment Programme Science Plan

Linking TRAKT project to the PEEX networking

Concentration and Deposition from Smelters of the Russian North: Atlas